

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LINGUOPRAGMATIC FEATURES OF COMMUNICATION BEHAVIOR OF PEOPLE IN VARIOUS JOB OCCUPATIONS

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Abstract: This article provides with the investigations of comparative linguopragmatic features of communication behavior of individuals in different job occupations. Through the research, the similarities and differences of occupational communicative behavior in English and Uzbek languages are determined and it is obviously stated that language and culture play a vital role in communicative behavior of people with different professions.

Key words: communication behavior, linguopragmatics, professional communication, formality and informality, hierarchy, brevity and accuracy, sincerity.

Annotatsiya: ushbu maqola turli kasb egalari muloqot xulqining qiyosiy lingvopragmatik xususiyatlarini tadqiq etadi. Tadqiqot davomida ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi kasbiy muloqot xulqining o'xshash va farqli tomonlari ochib berildi va bu jarayonda til va madaniyatning o'rni ahamiyatli ekanligi ta'kidlandi.

Kalit so'zlar: muloqot xulqi, lingvopragmatika, rasmiylik va norasmiylik, ierarxiya, qisqalik va aniqlik, samimiylik.

Аннотация: В данной статье проведен сравнительный анализ лингвопрагматических особенностей формирования коммуникативного поведения людей разных профессий на английском и узбекском языках. В рамках исследования выявлены сходства и различия в поведении профессионального общения на двух языках и указаны причины их возникновения. Результаты исследования показали важность роли языковых и культурных факторов в формировании коммуникативного поведения людей профессии.

Ключевые слова: коммуникативное поведение, лингвопрагматика, профессиональное общение, формальность и неформальность, иерархия, краткость и точность, искренность.

A wide range of factors contribute to the formation of communicative behavior of individuals with varying job occupations. Language and culture play a remarkable role in this point. Communicative behaviors in different professions have characteristic features in every society which can be obviously detected in their verbal and nonverbal conversations [1]. Taking these above into consideration, it can be claimed that the researches in the fields of learning differing communicative behaviors in different

professions can be of great benefit not only in enhancing the communication behavior but also in averting the misunderstandings in different cultures.

Several methods including comparative-descriptive method, linguopragmatic analysis and receptive experiment methods are applied while carrying out the research. Materials of the research are the audio and video recordings, fictional books including the conversations of different occupations and the extracts taken from the journalistic sources.

Professional communication is a very hot topic that is researched by many scientists, such as J.Holmes and M.Stubbenig [2;3]and in the scientific studies by T.Shiryaeva and D.Husanova [4;5]. These studies show that occupational communicative behavior is tightly connected with language and culture.

While doing the research, several differences and similarities of occupational communicative behavior in Uzbek and English languages as in the following:

A) Formality and informality. Both languages have the examples of formal and informal styles. Formal style is more protocol-based whereas the informal one obviously shows the sincere and friendly atmosphere.

B) Equality and hierarchy. It is distinctive that English communications in different professions are built in the norms of equality and are held in a far more friendly manner. The Uzbek communication behavior in various occupations emphasizes more the age, reputation and social status of individuals [6].

C) Accuracy and brevity. This point is more characteristic in English while Uzbek communication behavior uses deeper utterances and gestures and some other nonverbal devices as well.

D) Sincerity and friendliness. In formal occasions the Uzbek language pays peculiar attention to sincerity and friendliness and shows high respect to the addressee and in the English communication friendly atmosphere still remains in most of the cases[7]

The results gained via doing the research illustrate that the different and similar features of occupational communicative behavior are connected with the language and culture of the current society. The common use of informal and friendly language in English may define the superior individual's value in the society. Take the example of office

language where friendly and free conversation with the ones in charge is normally accepted. For example, it is considered to be a common case to address to the governing operators or to the ones in higher reputation with their names instead of using Mr. or Mrs. in big companies and start-ups. This also shows the society built on the more equal and free relationships[8]. Comparatively, in Uzbek these relationships are mostly built on the principles of hierarchy and strict set of rules. For instance, it is a common case to use “You” (Siz) to the addressee who is in authority and formal style of language is maintained. This shows the Uzbek people’s high value of respect[9].

Trying to reach the productivity in communication through the use of clear and short language is vividly seen in English. Take the examples of the English electronic messages: “please review and approve by EOD”. EOD (end of day) is an abbreviation used in business which means the end of working day. This is used to be clear and short in expressing the urgent message in English language. In Uzbek language it is more complex and in most cases transitional words and respectful phrases are used as in the example: “Iltimos, ushbu hujjatni ko’rib chiqing va imkon qadar tezroq tasdiqlang”[10].

In English and Uzbek languages, professional communication is connected with not only communication behavior but also with some other factors such as the participants’ individual characters, age, gender and degree of education. Young employees can have the communication with the governing ones in the workplace in a free and sincere manner. By this, they can express what they want without any barriers. In these kinds of communication, it is little or not felt the effect of age and status in the workplace and it is valued on professional competencies remarkably. In Uzbek language, young individuals should show high respect to the ones older than them and should not distract from what they are talking.

Participants’ individual experiences and view of the world affect the communication behavior as well. In English atmosphere, individuals can easily express their opinions and independently make decisions and that is considered important. One example is taken from corporative meetings: “I believe we should take this direction because...” which delivers the meaning to utter from their own opinion independently.

On the contrary, in Uzbek corporative meetings, main point is directed towards solidary and teamwork and mostly decisions are made according to the majority.

Another factor in professional language is gender. For example, the difference between male and female workers is almost unnoticeable in English communication. Commonly, women are also strict and clear in their communication. And in most cases, women can make strict decisions in a governing role as in the example: “We need to move forward with this plan”. In Uzbek communication women are mostly expected to be mild and sincere.

Language also plays an important role in professional communication behavior. Usually, in English language imperative sentences are made with milder ways such as modal verbs: “could you please finish this task by tomorrow?” however in Uzbek imperatives are used more as in the given example: “Ertaga bu ishni tugatib bering” (Finish the task by tomorrow). These kinds of differences are connected with the linguistic characteristics of the language and both languages demonstrate varying level of friendliness and strictness.

In the place of summary, it can be stated that the professional communication behavior gets formed by the influences of culture, gender, age and linguistic features. These factors altogether form the unique features of the professional language in different societies. Therefore, in researching this type of language, none of the points mentioned above should be neglected which also helps to understand cultural communication and avert the misunderstandings among different professions and cultures.

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